

Fault-Tolerance in Distributed Shared Memory through Process Replication

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This research proposes an algorithm for fault-tolerance in a home-based lazy release consistent distributed shared memory (HLRC-DSM). We propose the use of task replication so that the probability of all replicas failing becomes acceptably small. A management scheme for the replicated tasks is employed to keep data consistent while minimizing the overhead costs. The DSM architecture to support this is presented, with descriptions of the components. We also present simulation results showing how the amount of DSM synchronization and the degree of replication impact the number of messages passed and application execution times. With our approach, parallel applications continue to execute despite failure of processes provided that there are active replicas.

Keywords: Fault Tolerance, Distributed Shared Memory, Checkpoints, Message Logging, Replication

INTRODUCTION

Message passing is the traditional approach to parallel programming on systems like networks of workstations and clusters. However, message passing programming is low-level and consequently, very difficult. Distributed shared memory (DSM) aims to simplify this task by presenting a logical shared memory view of the system (Wijnberg, 2000). This view hides the remote communication mechanism from the programmers, thus making programming in distributed systems easier (Iftode, 1998; Protic et al., 1996).

Many parallel applications solve large computational problems in the sciences and engineering. These applications typically execute for long periods of time. If any machine fails while in the middle of such long-running application, the whole computation needs to be restarted. In order for DSM to be practical, it is important that, first, the system is recoverable when faults occur and, second, the computation need not restart due to such faults (Park and Yeom, 2000). This means that fault-tolerance in DSM is needed and techniques such as replication and checkpointing need to be incorporated.

HOME-BASED LAZY RELEASE CONSISTENCY MODEL (HLRC)

Distributed shared memory systems employ a memory consistency model which determines how applications “view” the behavior of the memory. Among these models is the lazy release consistency (LRC) model proposed by Peter Keleher (Keleher, 1995). LRC employs replication of the shared pages and diffs are used to update these (Cox et al., 1992). A “diff” contains the differences between the up-to-date copy of a page and a stale copy, reducing the need to send an entire page.

The home-based LRC (HLRC) model was proposed by Ifode (1998) to improve the performance of the lazy release consistency model. In LRC, the node may have to obtain diffs from several nodes, requiring multiple messages to be passed to serve a page fault. This may increase the size of messages since the node may have to obtain the message not only from the last writer, but from all the previous writers as well.

In the HLRC Model, every shared page has a designated home node, where all the other nodes visit to get the most up-to-date information. The home node’s copy of the page is eagerly updated, wherein the home node copy is updated at every release. Non-home copies are invalidated on the next acquire operation, just like in the standard LRC algorithm. Furthermore, the updates are fetched from the home node, instead of the previous writers.

FAULT-TOLERANCE TECHNIQUES

Research on fault-tolerance in DSMs has been ongoing for many years. One technique for fault-tolerance is to employ checkpoints which involves saving the state information of a system (Kalaiselvi and Rajaraman, 2000). With periodic checkpoints, the system can recover to a recent saved state to reduce the need for reprocessing.

Message-logging is typically combined with checkpoints. In message-logging, processes are required to save their states and log the messages they received after saving these states. When a process crashes, a new process takes its place. The

original local state, through the checkpoint, is sent to the new process. Lastly, based on the logs, messages are resent to the new process in the order they were originally received before the crash (Alvisi and Marzullo, 1998).

Another technique is replication. DSMs typically employ data replication. Data replication increases the availability of data when failures occur (Fleisch et al., 2000). Data on home nodes are replicated and the diff propagation is modified to ensure consistency (Christodoulopoulou et al., 2003).

Process replication has not received the same attention data replication has. This approach has been implemented on object-oriented environments (Beedubail et al., 1995; Cooper, 1985). A group of replicas of the same component is called a *troupe*. A troupe has a leader and other members are called cohorts. All troupe members perform identical roles and do not know of the existence of the other troupe members.

To the best of our knowledge, there has been no research implementing process replication on a DSM environment.

SYSTEM DESIGN

The architecture of the Fault-Tolerance System is illustrated in Figure 1. Each participating machine has an instance of the fault detection module (FD), the election / enrollment management module (EEM), the spawn module (SM), and the checkpoint / logging module (CL).

Figure 1. System Modules

When the DSM application is executed, the spawn module (SM) replicates processes in order to meet the desired degree of replication provided by the user. Figure 2 illustrates the flow of the whole spawning procedure.

Figure 2. Flowchart of Spawning replicas

The EEM is responsible for setting a leader-cohort setup. The module manages the troupe membership and elects a leader for each troupe.

The FD detects faults during run-time. When a failure has been detected, it will notify the EEM of the failure. The EEM will send a restart request to the spawn module. The SM will restart the failed process to maintain the degree of replication. Figure 3 illustrates this procedure.

The CL handles checkpoints and message logging, which are needed to maintain troupe consistency.

Figure 3. Module Interaction upon Failure

In this proposed system, every time a troupe enters a region where operations are visible to the global state of the system, they synchronize with the troupe leader. This synchronization happens at the acquire and release intervals.

Synchronization also occurs during page faults. For all operations outside the acquire and release intervals, synchronizations are not necessary.

When the troupe enters the critical section¹, the troupe leader must first acquire the lock. The cohorts wait for the leader to complete. The troupe leader, on the other hand, will send an acquire request to the last troupe that has acquired the lock. This message will be received by the EEM of the sending troupe leader and it will decide to which process the request will go. When the grant is sent to the requesting leader, it is piggybacked with the list of invalidates. The leader continues execution while all cohorts standby. When accessing the shared page, the leader sends the update request. The troupe leader logs all messages received during execution in the critical section. Should the troupe leader complete execution in the critical section, it will send a request for release piggybacked with its message log. Upon reception of the grant for release, the leader sends the logs to the waiting cohorts. The cohorts then execute in the critical

¹ Critical sections are signified by the acquire - release interval in release consistent models.

section locally while the troupe leader continues on. All troupe members are always in the same state at the next acquire request.

The troupe receiving the acquire request² employs a similar scheme. The troupe leader processes the request and logs the request. It sends the lock grant to the cohorts and then to the requesting troupe. On release, the receiving leader saves the message log of the releasing troupe and adds a grant to the log. The message log is discarded when confirmation of the release is done.

RECOVERY

If one of the cohorts fails, the global state of the system is unaffected. Hence, the execution can still continue. The EEM will trigger the recovery procedure for that process while the computation continues. The process is restarted using a checkpoint state from its fellow waiting cohorts.

If the leader of the troupe fails while in the critical section, the EEM must elect a new leader. Any replica can assume the leader role since the failed leader has not committed any computations. Figure 4 illustrates the flowchart of the recovery procedure.

The election involves finding a suitable cohort to replace the failed leader. Among the EEMs of the troupe concerned, there is a coordinator assigned upon recovery initiation from leader failure. The coordinator can be determined by a simple basis such as the highest process id. This coordinator selects the cohort through a deterministic selection procedure such as highest number of logs received. The new leader may have to repeat computations already performed by the failed leader.

Periodic checkpoints are still taken and used if troupe exhaustion occurs, i.e., all the troupe members fail. If troupe exhaustion occurs, the whole system will be forced to rollback to the latest checkpoint. Replica exhaustion is another case where all cohorts fail while the leader is still executing in the critical section. In such a scenario, should the leader complete execution in the critical

section, the state of the leader is used as a checkpoint.

Figure 4. Flowchart of Recovery

LIMITATIONS

The research assumes the network cluster is reliable and no messages are lost. This also includes message logs and checkpoints sent. Also, system processes such as the DSM system as well as the fault tolerance system processes do not fail in the

² The request is applicable to acquire, release, and page update (including home node page updates) requests.

duration of system execution. The fault detection mechanism is assumed to be reliable and responsive. The algorithm takes into account only two types of failures: node failure and process failure. Furthermore, processes waiting in the ready queue of a node can receive messages. During failure recovery, the recovery process must not experience another consecutive process failure.

SIMULATION RESULTS

The proposed method was simulated to evaluate its performance. Table 1 show the assumed time used in the simulation.

Table 1. Testing Parameters & Environment

Number of nodes	10	Release	1 time unit
Shared reads	1 time unit	Checkpoint	10 time units
Shared writes	2 time units	Checkpoint intervals	10 time units
Local operations	1 time unit	Rollback	10 time units
Acquire	1 time unit	Detection delay	5 time units

We considered three cases. The best-case scenario is defined as the scenario where only cohorts fail while execution is done. The election case is defined as the case where the leader fails during execution and election commences. Lastly, the worst case is the case where troupe failure occurs when failure is triggered. Performance is measured using execution time and messages sent. Replication degrees of two and three were used. All graphs are either number of messages passed or execution time of the whole simulation mapped against percent process failure event triggered. Figure 5 illustrates the execution times in the best-case scenario.

The best-case graph shows a decreasing trend, which is attributed to lighter loads when cohorts fail. The messages-passed-graph shows a completely opposite trend as shown in Figure 6. This is due to the need to keep cohorts consistent. The same trends on both graphs are seen on the worst-case scenario. Figure 7 and 8 show the results for the election case while Figure 9 and 10 are for the worst case.

Figure 5. Execution time in best case

Figure 6. Messages passed in best case

Figure 7. Execution time in election case

Figure 8. Messages passed in election case

Figure 9. Execution time in worst case

Figure 10. Messages passed in worst case

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

We have presented an algorithm for handling replicated processes and replicated data to give fault-tolerance to a DSM. By using synchronizations, consistency issues for replicas were addressed. In our preliminary tests, it is shown that the load is significantly increased when degrees of replication are increased. The execution time is affected not only by the degree but also by the amount of synchronization that must be done for each troupe. As the likelihood of process failures increase, the better the performance for the algorithm is as this would mean lesser load stress for the cluster. Messages passed significantly increases as well. The number of messages passed increase as the degree of replication increases. Due to the number of synchronizations needed, the network may get flooded with messages and cause a slowdown in the system. To get the maximum performance, an ideal degree of replication must be determined. Although

simulation tests show that the ideal degree is two, the simulation result is hardly definitive.

There are several avenues for future work. Further tests are needed to evaluate the performance of the algorithm. This would include using simulated tests and tests on an actual implementation. In addition, the algorithm can be extended to allow computation and data migration for better performance. Optimizations are necessary to decrease the messages sent and number of synchronizations necessary to preserve consistency. Messages sent to processes in the ready queue cannot be received and the algorithm has to be adjusted to reflect this particular issue since the algorithm assumes otherwise. The algorithm can also be extended to cover Byzantine faults to give reliability to safety-critical systems.

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